

Therapeutic potential of acetyl-DL-leucine and its L-enantiomer in posterior fossa syndrome: Mechanistic insights

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Posterior fossa syndrome (PFS) is a serious postoperative complication that primarily affects children following resection of posterior fossa tumors. Although its complex pathophysiology, involving disruption of cerebellar structures and the dentato-thalamo-cortical pathway, is increasingly being elucidated, effective treatments remain limited. This perspective explores acetyl-DL-leucine (ADLL) and its active L-enantiomer, N-acetyl-L-leucine (NALL), as promising therapeutic candidates for PFS. Emerging mechanistic, preclinical, and clinical evidence suggests that both compounds might alleviate PFS symptoms through neuroprotective and neurorestorative mechanisms, including neuronal membrane stabilization, metabolic enhancement, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects, and dopaminergic modulation. NALL, which has greater neurotherapeutic potential than ADLL, might particularly support recovery through its multimodal effects on neuronal function, thereby enhancing perioperative resilience. Further translational research into these acetylated leucine analogues is warranted.

Keywords: acetyl-DL-leucine; N-acetyl-L-leucine; levacylleucine; posterior fossa syndrome; cerebellar mutism; cerebellar dysfunction

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Introduction

PFS, also known as cerebellar mutism syndrome (CMS), is a constellation of symptoms including transient mutism, emotional lability, ataxia, oculomotor disturbances, and cranial nerve dysfunction that occurs predominantly in children after surgical resection of posterior fossa tumors, such as medulloblastomas. The syndrome is characterized by delayed onset of symptoms, typically 1 to 3 days after surgery, which persist for several months or even years. Epidemiological data indicate that PFS emerges in approximately 25–29% of pediatric patients following the resection of posterior fossa tumours.^{(p1),(p2),(p3),(p4),(p5),(p6)} This incidence underscores the considerable prevalence of PFS in this vulnerable population, highlighting the syndrome as a significant postoperative complication. The severity of symptoms in PFS varies widely, ranging from transient mutism and emotional lability to more persistent neurobehavioral and motor symptoms. According to Khan *et al.*,^(p7) PFS can be categorized into two types based on the severity of symptoms: type 1 with complete mutism and type 2 with reduced speech. Their study found that 34% of the children studied developed PFS after medulloblastoma resection. Of these, 23% had complete mutism (type 1), and 11% had reduced speech (type 2). All children with PFS had severe ataxia, and about 42.5% of those with type 1 PFS also had movement disorders. The course of recovery showed that speech and gait returned within a median of 2.3 to 2.1 months for type 1 PFS and within a shorter period for type 2 PFS. However, approximately 44.4% of type 1 children remained nonambulatory 1 year after surgery, highlighting the potential for long-term impairment. This variability highlights the complexity of PFS and the importance of tailored postoperative care.

The elucidation of predictive factors for PFS has been the focal point of numerous investigations, with the aim of improving prognostic precision and tailoring interventional strategies.^{(p8),(p9),(p10),(p11),(p12)} Age has been recognized as a significant factor, with younger patients exhibiting a heightened risk for developing PFS, underscoring the sensitivity of developing neural structures to surgical trauma.^{(p7),(p13)} The anatomical locus of the tumor plays a critical role, with vermian and midline tumors posing a greater risk because of their proximity to essential cerebellar and brainstem pathways.^{(p14),(p15),(p16),(p17)} The extent of tumor resection, particularly involving the cerebellar vermis, has been directly correlated with the incidence of PFS, highlighting the balance between oncological necessity and the preservation of neurological function.^{(p13),(p17)} Furthermore, surgical methodology and the experience of the surgical team have emerged as crucial determinants. High-volume centers and surgeons with extensive experience in posterior fossa surgeries report lower incidences of PFS, suggesting that surgical expertise significantly influences patient outcomes.^(p7) Recent studies have also highlighted the impact of intraoperative factors, such as blood loss, operative duration, and the advantageous role of intraoperative imaging, emphasizing the potentially modifiable nature of these risk factors.^{(p2),(p18),(p19)} Furthermore, preoperative neurological status and the presence of hydrocephalus have been discussed as potential predictors,

where pre-existing cerebellar dysfunction and increased intracranial pressure can predispose patients to PFS.^{(p2),(p12),(p18)}

Adjustments in surgical strategies, particularly the adoption of the telovelar approach, which is a sophisticated strategy to access the fourth ventricle and its surrounding structures without incising the cerebellar vermis,^{(p20),(p21)} have been associated with a lower incidence of PFS in pediatric patients after surgery in the posterior fossa. This approach significantly reduces the risk of disrupting critical cerebellar pathways, which are frequently implicated in the onset of PFS. Similarly, minimizing the use of cavitronic ultrasonic aspirators (CUSA) contributes to this reduction by enabling the selective removal of tumor tissue while preserving surrounding healthy brain tissue. Cobourn *et al.*^(p22) demonstrated that these refined surgical techniques significantly reduced the incidence of CMS from 39% to 10.8%. Conversely, findings from the Nordic-European study of CMS, involving a prospective observational multicenter investigation, indicate that the choice of surgical access route, specifically comparing the telovelar with the transvermian approach, does not appear to significantly impact the risk of postoperative speech impairment.^{(p23),(p24)}

Pathophysiology of PFS

The pathophysiology of PFS involves a multifactorial interplay of anatomical perturbations and physiological disturbances following posterior fossa surgery. Central to these mechanisms is damage to the dentato–thalamo–cortical (DTC) pathway, a critical neural circuit that facilitates cerebellar communication with the cerebral cortex.^{(p3),(p25),(p26)} Surgical interventions, particularly those that require resection of midline posterior fossa tumors, can directly disrupt this pathway, leading to hallmark symptoms of PFS such as mutism, ataxia, and emotional lability.^{(p26),(p27),(p28)} The elucidation of the pathophysiology of PFS is being advanced by the identification of pathological processes associated with the Guillain–Mollaret triangle (GMT), which includes the dentate nucleus, red nucleus, and inferior olivary nucleus. Using diffusion tensor imaging (DTI), microstructural abnormalities in the inferior olivary nuclei, specifically increased mean diffusivity and altered fractional anisotropy, have been demonstrated in PFS cases. This evidence points to GMT dysfunction as an important factor that affects motor and speech coordination and thus sheds light on neuroanatomical disturbances indicative of manifestations of PFS.^{(p29),(p30),(p31),(p32),(p33),(p34),(p35),(p36)}

Treatment of PFS

The initial surgical approach and meticulous postsurgical management play a critical role in patient outcomes, focusing on minimizing cerebellar damage and early intervention for PFS symptoms. Multidisciplinary team collaboration is essential to tailor these therapeutic strategies effectively to the specific needs of each patient, highlighting the personalized nature of treatment plans in the management of PFS.^{(p7),(p14),(p31),(p37)} Therapeutic modalities for PFS encompass a multidisciplinary approach tailored to address the complex and multifaceted symptomatology of the condition.

Nonpharmacological management of PFS

Intensive rehabilitation therapies are key interventions primarily involving occupational therapy, speech therapy, and physical therapy, each playing a crucial role in the gradual recovery of lost functions and helping patients adapt to daily activities.^{(p38),(p39),(p40)} Physical therapy emphasizes the restoration of motor skills through exercises that improve balance and coordination, which are often significantly altered in patients with PFS. Techniques such as vestibular rehabilitation have shown beneficial effects in improving gaze stability and postural control, thus positively contributing to the overall mobility and balance of affected children.^{(p41),(p42)} Speech therapy, in particular, is critical, as it addresses communication challenges, including mutism and speech apraxia, commonly associated with PFS. This therapy contributes significantly to recovery, helping patients regain their ability to communicate effectively, which is often compromised following surgery.^(p43) Furthermore, neuromodulation devices, including cranial nerve noninvasive neuromodulation (CN-NINM) and Brainport[®], have been used effectively in conjunction with intensive physical therapy.^(p44) These interventions not only improve motor function, but also induce significant neuroplastic changes crucial for long-term rehabilitation outcomes. Such combined therapies have been documented to result in notable improvements in motor skills in children after tumor treatment, enhancing their quality of life and alleviating the burdens of daily activities.^(p44) Integration of these therapies requires careful coordination within an interdisciplinary team that includes neurospecialists, therapists, and educational professionals to manage the extensive cognitive and physical deficits associated with PFS. The goal is to create a comprehensive treatment plan that not only focusses on immediate relief but also addresses long-term developmental needs and supports the child's reintegration into social and educational settings.

Pharmacological management of PFS

The pharmacological management of PFS remains a complex challenge in neurooncology practice, especially after surgical resection of posterior fossa tumors such as medulloblastoma. Despite the paucity of evidence on effective pharmacotherapy, some studies offer promising directions.

GABAergic modulation in PFS

GABAergic therapies have been explored as potential treatments for PFS, with some promising case studies and analyses providing insights into their efficacy. Among these, a retrospective analysis by AlAzmi *et al.*^(p45) explores the use of zolpidem, a non-benzodiazepine hypnotic, in pediatric patients with symptoms of PFS after tumor resection. The study included six patients characterized by clinical features such as irritability, hypotonia, and delayed speech. Treatment with zolpidem was initiated between 2 and 5 days postoperatively and continued for a median of 13.5 days. Promising results were observed, with 50% of patients showing recovery after speech within 2 weeks of starting treatment, and 83.3% regaining normal speech by month 4. However, not all patients achieved full ambulation. In addition, there were no discontinuations of treatment because of adverse effects. The therapeutic efficacy of zolpidem might be

attributable to its paradoxical stimulatory effect on the corticostriatopallidal–thalamocortical pathway, a neural circuit associated with mutism.

Another interesting finding related to the therapeutic influence of the GABAergic system in PFS is presented in a case report discussing the rapid effect of midazolam.^(p46) This case describes significant and rapid resolution of PFS after midazolam administration in a 17-year-old male patient who had undergone resection of a fourth ventricle choroid plexus papilloma. Before midazolam administration, single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) imaging revealed hypoperfusion in the left parietal and occipital lobes, the thalamus, and the right paramedian cerebellar region. Post-administration SPECT showed a marked improvement in perfusion in these regions, paralleling clinical recovery. This study suggests that midazolam might exert its effects on the thalamocortical circuit by potentiating GABAergic inhibition, which in turn affects the direct and indirect pathways of the basal ganglia. By enhancing striatal inhibition of the substantia nigra pars reticulata–globus pallidus internus (SNpr–Gpi) complex, midazolam could reduce thalamic inhibition and thereby increase cortical excitation. This mechanism might provide an explanation for the rapid improvement observed, although further research is needed to fully elucidate the underlying processes. This case adds to the growing evidence that GABAergic drugs such as zolpidem and midazolam modulate the DTC pathway in PFS.^{(p46),(p47),(p48),(p49)}

Dopaminergic and serotonergic modulation in PFS

Several case reports highlight the therapeutic influence of the dopaminergic system in PFS through the use of the dopamine D1/D2 receptor agonist bromocriptine.^{(p50),(p51),(p52)} In one case, an 18-year-old female developed akinetic mutism after total excision of a fourth ventricle choroid plexus papilloma. Initial treatment with antiedema therapy and lumbar punctures failed to improve her condition. However, after bromocriptine administration, the patient showed significant improvement, starting to speak and move within 24 h, with further improvement as the dose increased and good health maintained for 6 months.^(p51) Another report presented three pediatric cases who developed PFS after posterior fossa tumor surgery and were treated with bromocriptine. Starting with a low dose and gradually increasing to the minimum effective dose, the three patients showed significant improvement in speech and mobility over 4 months without adverse events.^(p50) These cases suggest that bromocriptine modulation of dopaminergic pathways might facilitate neurological recovery in patients with PFS.

Bromocriptine likely affects cortical excitation in a way similar to that of midazolam and zolpidem, but through different mechanisms. Midazolam and zolpidem enhance the inhibitory action on GABA_A receptors, increasing GABAergic inhibition in the brain. This reduces excitatory input from the striatum to the SNpr–Gpi complex, decreasing thalamic inhibition and increasing thalamic excitation of the cortex. In the indirect pathway, they reduce overall excitability, decreasing thalamic inhibition and enhancing cortical excitation.^(p46) Bromocriptine, a D2 dopamine receptor agonist, stimulates D2 receptors in the striatum, reducing GABAergic output to the globus pallidus externus (GPe). This increases the inhibition of the subthalamic nucleus

(STN), reduces the excitatory input to the SNpr–GPI complex, and decreases the inhibition of the thalamus, enhancing the cortical excitation. By improving dopaminergic tone, bromocriptine can also facilitate the direct pathway, further enhancing cortical excitation.^{(p53),(p54),(p55),(p56)} When considering the therapeutic effects of bromocriptine, it is essential to account for its significant influence on the serotonergic system, attributed to its agonistic action on the 5-HT_{2A} and 5-HT_{2C} receptors.^{(p57),(p58)} Based on understanding of the interplay between the serotonergic and dopaminergic systems, it can be hypothesized that bromocriptine activation of 5-HT_{2A} and 5-HT_{2C} receptors promotes neuroplasticity by enhancing synaptic connectivity, thus supporting learning and memory functions.^{(p59),(p60),(p61)} The 5-HT_{2A} and 5-HT_{2C} receptors exhibit a close physical association within the medial prefrontal cortex, regulating executive function, decision making, and reward-guided learning and memory processes. Furthermore, its colocalization in prefrontal cortex neurons, along with bromocriptine's agonistic action, suggests a synergistic effect, enhancing cortical excitability and refining cognitive output.^{(p62),(p63)} Additionally, 5-HT_{2C} receptor activation enhances dopamine's influence on cortical functions, augmenting dopaminergic signaling and supporting optimal cognitive performance.^{(p63),(p64),(p65)}

In the context of the positive findings related to bromocriptine mentioned above, it is important to note that dopaminergic drugs, which act as agonists on both the D₁ and D₂ receptors, can exhibit a significantly more pronounced procognitive effect because of their synergistic action. For instance, it has been demonstrated that, following mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI), the mixed D₁/D₂ agonist pergolide is more effective than bromocriptine in improving working memory performance. Moreover, pergolide was associated with greater activation of neural circuits related to working memory, particularly in the left inferior frontal gyrus.^(p66) Thus it is possible that treatment with D₁/D₂ mixed agonists might also be promising in the treatment of PFS.

Another pharmacological option for managing the symptoms of PFS is the antidepressant fluoxetine. Classified as a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), fluoxetine is recognized primarily for its antidepressant effects. It has also shown promising results in the treatment of selective mutism, indicating its potential usefulness beyond psychiatric applications and extending towards neuropsychological symptoms. A case report of a pediatric patient with cerebellar mutism after medulloblastoma resection demonstrated a significant improvement with fluoxetine administration, despite the initial deterioration with standard treatment.^{(p47),(p67),(p68)} A study conducted at the University Hospital of Angers reviewed the outcomes of 246 pediatric patients admitted for brain surgery, 23 of whom had been diagnosed with CMS and eight of whom had been treated with fluoxetine. Although the study confirmed the safety profile of fluoxetine, it did not demonstrate efficacy in reducing the duration of mutism. Given that treatment was initiated after recovery from complete mutism in half of the treated patients, the statistical power of these findings is questionable.^(p69) In the context of the above findings regarding fluoxetine treatment, it is crucial to recognize the difference in symptomatology between CMS and PFS, particularly because the findings relate primarily to

mutism rather than to the general symptomatology of PFS. CMS is predominantly characterized by mutism and emotional lability, focusing narrowly on these aspects, whereas PFS encompasses a wider range of symptoms, often including motor disturbances.^(p70)

Experimental pharmacotherapy in PFS

From the perspective of experimental pharmacotherapy, the use of monoclonal antibodies appears to be a promising option for the treatment of PFS. A case report by Signoriello *et al.*^(p71) demonstrated the therapeutic potential of alemtuzumab, a monoclonal antibody that selectively targets the CD52-a protein, which is ubiquitously expressed on the surface of mature lymphocytes. The report documents the clinical efficacy in a 24-year-old patient with multiple sclerosis who developed a complex motor, cognitive, and behavioral syndrome following an extensive pontomesencephalic lesion during fingolimod treatment. However, the pathophysiology of the postoperative lesion in PFS is markedly different from the demyelinating process in multiple sclerosis, raising questions about the applicability of alemtuzumab treatment to postoperative PFS cases.

Another experimental treatment awaiting validation by randomized controlled trials (RCTs) is based on an approach aimed at reducing early and late postoperative neuroinflammatory processes that damage neural tissue and impede repair processes. The tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) inhibitor etanercept has demonstrated significant clinical efficacy in the treatment of sequelae of traumatic brain injury (TBI) and both acute and persistent symptoms following stroke.^{(p72),(p73),(p74),(p75)} It is plausible that etanercept might also be effective in treating acute or chronic PFS. However, there are currently no established guidelines for the use of etanercept in pediatric neurooncology, so fundamental safety issues need to be addressed before a research protocol can be developed. Notably, a promising preclinical study^(p76) demonstrated that TNF- α inhibition suppressed medulloblastoma progression *in vivo*, suggesting potential antitumor effects and indicating that etanercept might not increase the likelihood of medulloblastoma recurrence, whose removal often leads to PFS symptoms. Despite positive neurological findings related to etanercept, clinical evidence remains limited to data from a single clinical site, underscoring the need for broader validation through comprehensive multicenter studies.

Acetyl-DL-leucine

ADLL is a modified amino acid derived from leucine, a branched-chain amino acid introduced in 1957 and used as a therapeutic agent under the brand name Tanganil™ for the treatment of acute vertigo in France and former French colonies. ADLL is administered orally and is recognized for its favorable safety profile, consistently documented in ongoing safety evaluations by its original French manufacturer. In the last decade, it has gained attention for its therapeutic potential in various neurological disorders. In addition to vertigo, the indications studied for ADLL include cerebellar ataxia^{(p77),(p78),(p79)} and migraine,^(p80) while clinical studies of rare neurodegenerative diseases, including Niemann–Pick disease type C,^{(p81),(p82)} GM2 gangliosidosis (a lysosomal storage disorder),^(p83) and ataxia–telangiectasia,^{(p84),(p85)} have been conducted with the isolated L-enantiomer, NALL.

The pharmacological effects of ADLL are enantiomer-specific (Figure 1), with NALL demonstrating significantly greater neurotherapeutic properties than N-acetyl-D-leucine (NADL).^{(p86),(p87)} Preclinical and clinical research suggests that NALL, but not NADL, can effectively reduce disease progression and improve motor function by influencing glucose metabolism and antioxidant pathways in neurodegenerative diseases.^{(p82),(p87)} This enantioselective profile is primarily attributable to pharmacokinetic differences, explained by a combination of mechanisms affecting absorption and metabolism. Following oral administration of the 1:1 racemate, the D-enantiomer exhibits higher affinity for the intestinal monocarboxylate transporter 1 (MCT1; $K_m = 1.0$ mM) compared with the L-enantiomer ($K_m = 3.0$ mM), and competitively saturates it, thereby limiting the uptake of NALL. In parallel, an intestinal and hepatic acylase, exhibiting a stereoselectivity exceeding 40 000-fold, preferentially deacetylates NALL to L-leucine while largely sparing NADL. As a result, NALL is rapidly metabolized and cleared, whereas NADL persists and accumulates systemically. Together, these mechanisms result in approximately 25-fold greater systemic exposure to NADL compared with NALL, as reflected by the maximum plasma concentration (C_{max} ; 86 100 vs 3410 ng ml⁻¹) and the area under the plasma concentration–time curve from zero to the last measurable concentration (AUC_{0-last} ; 75 800 vs 2560 h·ng ml⁻¹). In contrast, when pure NALL is administered, it avoids transporter-level competition from the D-enantiomer and achieves substantially greater systemic exposure (C_{max} 16 800 ng ml⁻¹; AUC_{0-last} 11 400 h·ng ml⁻¹).^{(p87),(p88)}

The enantioselective profile of NALL is not limited to differences in systemic pharmacokinetics, but also extends to tissue distribution and intracellular fate, both of which are critical for achieving therapeutic efficacy. Although the parent amino acid leucine is a zwitterion transported by the high-affinity but readily saturable L-type amino acid transporter 1 (LAT1), N-acetylation transforms it into a more lipophilic, anionic

compound that is preferentially taken up via alternative, LAT1-independent transport mechanisms. Cellular entry of NALL is instead mediated primarily by MCT1, which has been identified as a principal transporter for this compound and is abundantly expressed throughout the brain and blood–brain barrier.^{(p88),(p89),(p90),(p91)} However, the higher affinity of the D-enantiomer for MCT1 might interfere with the uptake of the therapeutically active L-enantiomer in target tissues. In addition, this enantioselectivity extends to intracellular metabolism: NALL is readily deacetylated to yield bioactive L-leucine, whereas the D-enantiomer is inefficiently processed and has been shown to persist in the brain in unmetabolized form.^{(p87),(p88)} These combined differences in transport and metabolism reinforce the rationale for pursuing the L-enantiomer as the preferred clinical candidate.

Clinical evidence for ADLL and NALL

Over the past decade, ADLL and its pharmacologically active L-enantiomer NALL have progressed from exploratory observations to prospectively powered, randomized trials across a remarkably diverse set of neurological and lysosomal storage disorders (Table 1). In the open-label case series, 13 patients with sporadic or genetic cerebellar ataxia who received 5 g day⁻¹ ADLL for 7 to 10 days demonstrated a mean 3.3-point reduction in the Scale for the Assessment and Rating of Ataxia (SARA) score together with clinically relevant gains in quality of life and an absence of drug-related adverse events.^(p92) The subsequent double-blind ALCAT crossover trial ($n = 108$) rigorously tested the same dose and found no superiority over placebo after 6 weeks, although the study importantly mapped the magnitude of placebo responses in ataxia and confirmed the compound's excellent tolerability profile.^(p78)

Proof-of-concept findings have also emerged outside the ataxia field. In a prospective case series involving ten patients with migraine, prophylactic administration of 3 g day⁻¹ ADLL over 12 weeks resulted in a $\geq 50\%$ reduction in monthly migraine

FIGURE 1

Stereochemical structures of acetylated leucine derivatives investigated in the context of posterior fossa syndrome (PFS). **(a)** Acetyl-DL-leucine (ADLL), a racemic formulation comprising equimolar amounts of the D- and L-enantiomers of N-acetylated leucine. **(b)** N-acetyl-L-leucine (NALL), the enantiomerically pure L-isomer. The stereochemical divergence between these two compounds is of clinical significance, as accumulating evidence suggests differential efficacy in the treatment of PFS.

TABLE 1

Clinical studies of acetyl-DL-leucine and acetyl-L-leucine in selected neurological and lysosomal storage disorders^a

Diagnosis	Key study (first author, year)	Design/Phase	n	Dose & duration	Primary/relevant endpoints	Main outcome	Notes
Cerebellar ataxia	Strupp 2013 ^(p92)	Prospective open-label case series	13	5 g/day ADLL × 7–10 days	SARA, SCAFI, EQ-5D-3L	Mean SARA ↓ 3.3 pts (p = 0.002); QoL ↑; no AEs	Short exposure
	Feil 2021 (ALCAT) ^(p78)	Multicenter DB RCT, crossover, Phase II	108	5 g/day ADLL × 2 × 6 weeks (wash out)	ΔSARA at 6 weeks	No superiority vs placebo (Δ 0.23 pts; 95% CI – 0.40–0.85); well tolerated	Largest cerebellar ataxia trial to date
Migraine (± aura)	Strupp 2019 ^(p80)	Prospective case series	10	3 g/day ADLL, 12 weeks	Monthly migraine days; aura frequency	7/10 ≥ 50% attack reduction; no serious AEs	First human data
Niemann–Pick C	Bremova Ertl 2024 ^(p81)	Multinational DB RCT, crossover, Phase III	60	4 g/day NALL ≥ 13 years; 2–4 g/day 4–12 years (weight-based); 2 × 12 weeks	ΔSARA (primary); CGI-I, mDRS	LS mean Δ – 1.28 pts vs placebo (p < 0.001); AE profile similar to placebo	Supported September 2024 FDA approval of levacetylleucine (Aqneursa [®])
GM2 gangliosidosis	Martakis 2023 ^(p83)	Multicenter open label, rater blinded, Phase IIb	30	4 g/day NALL ≥ 13 years; weight tiered < 13 y; 6 weeks + wash out	CI CS (8 MWT/9-HPT); ataxia scores	Primary met (mean diff 0.71; p = 0.039); QoL ↑; no serious AEs	Exploratory
Ataxia–telangiectasia	Brueggemann 2022 ^(p96)	Open-label case series	6	3–5 g/day ADLL ≥ 1 month	SARA; DBN SPV	SARA ↓ 4.1 pts (p = 0.003); DBN SPV ↓ 0.9°/s (p = 0.046); no serious AEs	Downbeat nystagmus improved
	Beyraghi Tousi 2024 ^(p95)	DB RCT, 2 × 2 crossover	16 (completed)	1–4 g/day NALL, 6 weeks	SARA, SCAFI, PedsQL	No significant motor benefit; GI symptoms improved; no serious AEs	First placebo controlled active treatment trial
Multiple sulfatase deficiency	Saberi Karimian 2023 ^(p85)	Single patient placebo controlled crossover	1	3 g/day NALL, 4 weeks	SARA, IL-6, QoL	SARA ↓ 25%; QoL ↑; no biochemical toxicity	Proof of concept

^a Abbreviations: 8MWT, 8-Meter Walk Test; 9HPT, 9-Hole Peg Test; ADLL, acetyl-DL-leucine; AE, adverse event; CI, confidence interval; CGI-I, Clinical Global Impression-Improvement; CI-CS, Clinical Impression of Change in Severity; DBN, downbeat nystagmus; DB-RCT, double-blind randomized controlled trial; EQ-5D-3L, EuroQoL five-dimension, three-level questionnaire; LS, least-squares (mean estimate); mDRS, modified Disability Rating Scale; NALL, acetyl-L-leucine; PedsQL, Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory; pts, points; QoL, quality of life; SARA, Scale for the Assessment and Rating of Ataxia; SCAFI, Spinocerebellar Ataxia Functional Index; SPV, slow-phase velocity.

days in seven individuals, with no safety concerns reported.^(p80) In the context of orphan neurodegenerative disease, a pivotal multicenter, double-blind, Phase III crossover study in 60 individuals with Niemann–Pick type C demonstrated that 12 weeks of weight-adjusted NALL (2–4 g day⁻¹) produced a least-squares mean improvement of –1.28 points on the SARA scale compared with placebo, together with improvements on the Clinical Global Impression-Improvement (CGI-I) and modified Disability Rating Scale.^(p81) These data provided the basis for the US FDA’s September 2024 approval of levacetylleucine (the international nonproprietary name for NALL), which is now marketed as Aqneursa[®].^{(p93),(p94)} The approval establishes a clear translational continuum from experimental compound to first-in-class therapy, thereby underscoring the clinical relevance of the molecule evaluated in the present work.

Efficacy signals are being replicated across other lysosomal storage disorders: a rater-blinded Phase IIb study in 30 patients with GM2 gangliosidosis met its primary Clinical Impression of Change in Severity end-point (mean difference 0.71, $p = 0.039$) after 6 weeks of NALL, with concomitant quality-of-life gains and no serious adverse events.^(p83) In ataxia–telangiectasia, a 16-patient double-blind crossover trial of 1–4 g day⁻¹ NALL over 6 weeks confirmed gastrointestinal tolerability but has not yet translated into a significant SARA benefit, highlighting disease-specific therapeutic challenges.^(p95) Small exploratory clinical series provide further supportive evidence. In patients with ataxia–telangiectasia, ADLL improved SARA by 4.1 points and reduced the slow-phase velocity of downbeat nystagmus in six adults.^(p96) Moreover, a placebo-controlled, single-patient crossover study conducted in patients with multiple sulfatase deficiency reported a 25% SARA reduction following NALL treatment, accompanied by meaningful improvements in quality of life.^(p97)

Collectively these convergent data, spanning open-label exploration and regulatory Phase III success, frame acetylated leucine derivatives as a clinically versatile and increasingly substantiated therapeutic platform. They supply both the mechanistic rationale and the regulatory precedent that motivate the present investigation of NALL in postoperative PFS.

Mechanism of action

Neurostabilizing effects of ADLL on vestibular neurons

ADLL has demonstrated significant neurostabilizing properties, particularly by normalizing the membrane potential in vestibular neurons affected by vestibular dysfunction. In a guinea pig model of unilateral labyrinthectomy (UL), ADLL effectively restored disrupted membrane potentials in vestibular neurons. Intracellular electrophysiological recordings indicate that the neurostabilizing action of ADLL depends on the resting membrane potential of the neurons. Specifically, ADLL hyperpolarizes neurons with elevated membrane potentials and depolarizes excessively hyperpolarized neurons, thereby stabilizing neuronal activity around the physiological resting membrane potential range of approximately –65 to –60 mV.^{(p98),(p99)} This stabilization of neuronal membrane potential is essential for maintaining proper neuronal excitability, preventing excessive depolarization

or hyperpolarization that could otherwise lead to abnormal signaling within the vestibular system. By restoring membrane potential, ADLL helps to alleviate symptoms of vestibular dysfunction, such as vertigo, by rebalancing neuronal activity between affected vestibular structures.^{(p100),(p101)}

Previous literature has speculated on a possible direct interaction between ADLL or its active enantiomer NALL and membrane phospholipids such as phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂). However, a primary study^(p102) using infrared (IR) spectroscopy in combination with Langmuir monolayer techniques found no evidence for significant direct interactions between ADLL or NALL and membrane phospholipids. In particular, detailed experiments used monolayers of phospholipids commonly found in biological membranes, including 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), a zwitterionic molecule, and 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoglycerol (DPPG), an anionic molecule. Even at higher concentrations, ADLL or NALL did not significantly intercalate into or interact with these lipid models, indicating the absence of direct phospholipid membrane interactions.

Stabilization of cerebellar neurons

Because of the phylogenetic and electrophysiological similarities between vestibular and deep cerebellar neurons, as well as their close functional interactions, ADLL is hypothesized to stabilize membrane potential in cerebellar neurons in a manner similar to its effects on vestibular neurons.^(p103) Specifically, ADLL likely stabilizes the membrane potential of cerebellar Purkinje cells, which are essential for motor control through their synaptic connections with the deep cerebellar nuclei. Purkinje cells exert powerful inhibitory effects on cerebellar nuclei through GABAergic projections, and excitatory input from mossy and climbing fibers modulates their firing properties. By stabilizing the membrane potential of Purkinje cells, ADLL might modulate afferent and efferent signaling within cerebellar circuits, exerting downstream effects on the brainstem, thalamus, and spinal cord.^(p104) This modulation could enhance cerebellar output, thereby improving motor coordination and potentially alleviating deficits in ataxic disorders and cerebellar dysarthria.

Enhancement of vestibulocerebellar compensation

In a recent investigation using a rat model of UL, the effects of ADLL, NALL, and NADL on central vestibular compensation were evaluated by behavioral testing and [¹⁸F]fluorodeoxyglucose ([¹⁸F]FDG) micro-positron emission tomography (μ PET) imaging.^(p105) Among the tested compounds, NALL significantly enhanced postural recovery, suggesting it has superior efficacy in accelerating vestibular compensation. This effect was correlated with an increase in regional cerebral glucose metabolism (rCGM) in the vestibulocerebellum and a decrease in rCGM in the posterolateral thalamus and subthalamic region. These findings suggest that NALL can promote recovery from vestibular damage by activating the vestibulocerebellum and modulating thalamic processing, facilitating the motor and sensory integration critical for postural control.

Modulation of energy metabolism and antioxidant defenses

ADLL exerts a profound influence on energy metabolism and antioxidant defenses within neurons, which are critical for maintaining cellular homeostasis under stress conditions such as cerebellar dysfunction or neurodegeneration. One of the key mechanisms involves the modulation of glucose metabolism through activation of the pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (PDH), a central enzyme in aerobic energy production. By enhancing PDH activity and reducing its inhibitory phosphorylation, ADLL promotes the efficient conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-coenzyme A (CoA), thus increasing flux through the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and increasing adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production.^(p82) This shift towards oxidative metabolism reduces reliance on anaerobic glycolysis, thus lowering lactate accumulation and improving overall neuronal energy efficiency.^(p106) Furthermore, NALL is taken up by neurons via MCT1, which can operate in a bidirectional exchange mode involving lactate. This proton-coupled mechanism enables NALL influx along concentration gradients and might favor its accumulation in brain tissues where elevated intracellular lactate levels drive enhanced uptake, such as under conditions of increased metabolic demand.^(p88) Alongside its role in regulating cellular energy metabolism, the enantiomer NALL enhances the antioxidant capacity of neurons by modulating mitochondrial oxidative stress pathways. By increasing the activity of mitochondrial enzymes such as superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2), NALL mitigates the harmful effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are commonly elevated during neurodegenerative processes. This increase in SOD2 activity helps reduce oxidative damage, thus protecting neuronal integrity, particularly in regions like the cerebellum and vestibular nuclei.^{(p107),(p108)} The superior antioxidant effects of NALL play a critical role in maintaining cellular health under conditions of metabolic stress, providing a robust defense against ROS-induced neuronal damage and further supporting synaptic stability and motor coordination.^(p82)

Anti-inflammatory mechanism

Among the important mechanisms of action is the preclinically observed anti-inflammatory effect of ADLL, as demonstrated in a study on its L-enantiomer NALL. In a model of TBI, NALL significantly reduced the expression of proinflammatory cytokines, including interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) and interferon beta (IFN- β), while upregulating anti-inflammatory markers such as suppressor of cytokine signaling 3 (SOCS3).^(p109) This anti-inflammatory effect could potentially reduce damaging neuroinflammation, a significant contributor to neuronal damage in various pathological conditions.^{(p110),(p111)} In addition, by reducing inflammation, ADLL might be able to support neuronal recovery and repair, potentially improving the healing process after neurosurgical procedures.^{(p112),(p113),(p114)}

Effects on dopaminergic neurotransmission

ADLL appears to significantly influence dopaminergic neurotransmission, as evidenced by its effects on the dopamine transporter (DAT) and dopaminergic pathways in individuals with prodromal Parkinson's disease (PD), specifically those suffering from isolated REM sleep behavior disorder (iRBD).^(p115) Long-

term ADLL treatment demonstrated a marked improvement in DAT binding within the nigrostriatal system, which is crucial in Parkinson's pathology. In a case study,^(p115) patients showed an increase in striatal DAT binding ratios, as observed by DAT-SPECT imaging, following several months of ADLL administration. This reversal of the progressive decline in DAT binding, typically associated with the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in PD, suggests that ADLL could exert a neuroprotective effect on dopaminergic neurons by stabilizing or even restoring dopaminergic function. Furthermore, although limited, evidence that ADLL affects the dopaminergic system in subcortical motor regions comes from a case study^(p116) that shows its efficacy in the treatment of restless legs syndrome (RLS). The patient, treated with a daily dose of 5 g of ADLL, experienced a significant reduction in severity from 'severe' to 'mild' after 4 weeks. This suggests that ADLL might modulate the pathological functioning of the nigrostriatal pathway and the cortico-striato-thalamo-cortical loop, the key circuit involved in the motor control and dopaminergic regulation that are disrupted in RLS. In the context of the above findings, it is particularly interesting that an autoradiography study in *Macaca fascicularis* monkeys showed that ADLL accumulates in brain areas key to the dopaminergic system, including the putamen, globus pallidus, and substantia nigra, all of which play critical roles in motor control and dopaminergic neurotransmission.^(p117) The presence of ADLL in these areas suggests that its neuroprotective effects can extend to enhancing dopaminergic signaling in these critical motor regions.

Proposed synergistic mechanism of action

Based on the previously presented findings, a synergistic mechanism of action for ADLL can be proposed. The observed increase in DAT binding in key dopaminergic regions, such as the putamen and globus pallidus, following ADLL treatment suggests that ADLL enhances dopaminergic signaling. This is further supported by autoradiography studies showing that ADLL accumulates in these critical motor regions. The enhanced binding of DAT might work in concert with the ability to modulate glucose metabolism and reduce oxidative stress, creating an optimal metabolic environment that supports neuronal function. By improving mitochondrial function and promoting energy efficiency through activation of the PDH, ADLL likely helps preserve neuronal integrity. Together, these mechanisms of enhanced DAT binding and improved metabolic support might act synergistically to protect dopaminergic neurons and slow the axonal degeneration commonly observed in central motor system disorders.

Effects of ADLL and NALL on the pathophysiology of PFS

The therapeutic potential of ADLL/NALL in neurological disorders characterized by cerebellar dysfunction and ataxia offers a promising avenue to address the complex symptomatology of PFS. Given the intricate pathophysiological mechanisms underlying PFS, which encompass disruptions in neuronal excitability, metabolic dysfunction, oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and neurotransmitter imbalances, the diverse pharmacodynamic

actions might confer significant benefits by targeting several key aspects of neuronal dysfunction resulting from surgical intervention (Figure 2).

Stabilization of neuronal membrane potential

A central component of the pathophysiology of PFS involves disruptions in neuronal excitability within cerebellar circuits, particularly affecting Purkinje cells and deep cerebellar nuclei. Purkinje cells are the principal output neurons of the cerebellar

cortex, providing inhibitory GABAergic input to the deep cerebellar nuclei, which in turn project to various motor and cognitive regions of the brain.^{(p118),(p119),(p120)} Surgical trauma to the posterior fossa can alter this delicate balance by causing direct injury to these neurons or their afferent and efferent connections, leading to altered firing patterns and impaired synaptic transmission.^{(p3),(p120)} As previously described, ADLL has been shown to stabilize neuronal membrane potentials in vestibular neurons and is hypothesized to exert similar effects in cerebellar

FIGURE 2

Proposed therapeutic mechanisms of acetyl-DL-Leucine (ADLL) in posterior fossa syndrome (PFS). ADLL, specifically its active enantiomer N-acetyl-L-leucine (NALL), holds potential therapeutic promise for PFS. Proposed mechanisms include: (i) stabilization of neuronal membrane potentials in Purkinje cells and deep cerebellar nuclei (DCN), restoring cerebellar firing and motor coordination; (ii) enhancement of mitochondrial energy metabolism via increased pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (PDC) activity, acetyl-CoA production, tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle flux, and mitochondrial adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis, leading to improved neuronal metabolism; (iii) reduction of oxidative stress through upregulation of mitochondrial superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2) and reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenging; (iv) modulation of anti-inflammatory signaling by reducing the proinflammatory cytokines interleukin 1 beta (IL-1 β) and nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), increasing the anti-inflammatory mediator interleukin-10 (IL-10), and upregulating suppressor of cytokine signaling 3 (SOCS3), thus lowering neuroinflammation and promoting tissue repair; and (v) enhancement of dopaminergic neurotransmission through augmented dopamine transporter (DAT) binding in nigrostriatal pathways, restoring dopaminergic tone, disinhibiting thalamocortical drive, and modulating cortico-striato-thalamo-cortical (CSTC) networks, which could normalize cortical excitability and enhance motor and speech functions.

circuits.^{(p98),(p99)} ADLL hyperpolarizes abnormally depolarized cells and depolarizes excessively hyperpolarized cells, thereby restoring membrane potentials towards the physiological range. This bidirectional correction might counteract aberrant neuronal activity arising from surgical injury. Restoring the membrane potential of cerebellar neurons could attenuate the aberrant firing patterns and synaptic transmission deficits that contribute to the motor and speech disturbances observed in PFS. Stabilization of Purkinje cell activity ensures appropriate inhibitory control over the deep cerebellar nuclei, which is essential for the coordination of motor outputs and modulation of cognitive processes. This stabilization could mitigate the excessive neuronal excitability or depression that underpins symptoms such as mutism, ataxia, and emotional lability. Moreover, by preserving the integrity of cerebellar output, ADLL might facilitate the reestablishment of normal communication between the cerebellum and higher cortical areas, thereby promoting the recovery of both the motor and nonmotor functions affected in PFS.

Enhancement of neuronal energy metabolism

Surgical intervention in the posterior fossa can precipitate metabolic dysfunction in neuronal populations caused by disrupted blood flow, hypoxia, and mitochondrial impairment.^{(p121),(p122)} Energy deficits can lead to impaired neuronal function, decreased synthesis of essential proteins, and activation of apoptotic pathways.^{(p123),(p124)} Neurons within the cerebellum have metabolic demands and rely heavily on oxidative phosphorylation for energy.^(p125) This dependency makes the cerebellum highly susceptible to metabolic disruption during surgical stress, where reduced oxygen supply and mitochondrial dysfunction can significantly alter energy metabolism, ultimately contributing to postoperative complications. ADLL has been shown to enhance glucose metabolism through the activation of the PDH, a pivotal enzyme that links glycolysis to the TCA cycle. By promoting the conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA, ADLL increases ATP production through oxidative phosphorylation within mitochondria. This shift towards increased aerobic metabolism improves energy production and reduces the accumulation of lactate and associated acidosis, which can be detrimental to neuronal viability.^(p82) By strengthening neuronal energy reserves, ADLL might support the metabolic demands of neurons during recovery and promote neuroplasticity. Adequate ATP levels are crucial for processes such as axonal transport, ion homeostasis, and the synthesis of the neurotransmitters and structural proteins required for synaptic repair and remodelling.^(p126) This metabolic support is particularly critical in cerebellar neurons, which have extensive dendritic arborization and rapid firing rates, making them especially vulnerable to energy deficits.^{(p127),(p128)} Enhanced energy metabolism induced by ADLL might also mitigate the activation of energy-sensing stress pathways, such as AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), which, when overactivated, can inhibit the anabolic processes necessary for neuronal recovery.^{(p129),(p130)} Furthermore, improved mitochondrial function can reduce the generation of ROS, decreasing oxidative stress and preventing damage to cellular components.^(p131) By improving both energy production and reducing metabolic stress, ADLL can create a more favorable environment for neuronal survival and functional recovery in PFS.

Antioxidant and neuroprotective effects

Oxidative stress is a critical mediator of neuronal injury in PFS, arising from an imbalance between the production of ROS and the capacity of antioxidant defenses following surgical intervention.^(p132) The excessive ROS that is generated can lead to lipid peroxidation, DNA fragmentation, and protein oxidation within cerebellar neurons, particularly affecting Purkinje cells and neurons of the deep cerebellar nuclei. This oxidative damage disrupts mitochondrial function, alters ATP production, and activates apoptotic pathways, culminating in neuronal loss and synaptic dysfunction.^(p133) Such cellular and molecular disturbances contribute to the motor deficits, mutism, and emotional lability characteristic of PFS by disrupting the integrity of cerebellar circuits essential for motor coordination and cognitive processing. NALL, the active enantiomer of ADLL, exhibits significant antioxidant properties that can ameliorate these deleterious effects. NALL enhances the activity of mitochondrial antioxidant enzymes, notably SOD2, which catalyzes the dismutation of superoxide radicals into hydrogen peroxide and oxygen, thus reducing the intracellular accumulation of ROS.^{(p107),(p108)} By bolstering the endogenous antioxidant defense system, NALL mitigates oxidative damage to cellular membranes, nucleic acids, and proteins, preserving mitochondrial integrity and preventing the initiation of intrinsic apoptotic pathways. In the context of PFS, the neuroprotective effects of NALL might contribute to the preservation of cerebellar neuronal integrity and the maintenance of functional synaptic connections. By protecting neurons from oxidative stress-induced injury, NALL could facilitate the restoration of disrupted cerebellar networks, promoting recovery of motor coordination and speech functions. Additionally, the antioxidative action of NALL can enhance neuronal resilience, supporting the neuroplastic changes necessary for compensatory mechanisms following cerebellar injury. Thus the capacity of NALL to reduce oxidative stress might play a pivotal role in counteracting the pathophysiological processes underlying PFS, offering a therapeutic avenue to improve clinical outcomes.

Anti-inflammatory effect

Surgical intervention in the posterior fossa can trigger an inflammatory response characterized by the activation of microglia and astrocytes, leading to the release of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-6.^{(p112),(p113),(p114)} This inflammatory milieu contributes to neuronal dysfunction through mechanisms including excitotoxicity mediated by excessive glutamate release, disruption of the blood-brain barrier, and promotion of secondary neuronal injury via oxidative stress and apoptosis.^{(p110),(p111),(p134)} The sustained neuroinflammatory response can alter synaptic plasticity and neurogenesis within the cerebellum, hindering the recovery of motor coordination and speech functions disrupted in PFS. The enantiomer NALL of ADLL has been observed to exert anti-inflammatory effects, potentially attenuating these pathological processes.^(p109) By downregulating the expression of proinflammatory cytokines and upregulating anti-inflammatory mediators such as interleukin-10 (IL-10) and SOCS3, NALL can modulate the inflammatory response. This modulation might involve the inhibition of key signaling pathways, including nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), which are central

regulators of inflammatory gene expression.^(p135) By suppressing microglial activation and cytokine production, NALL could reduce the propagation of inflammation within cerebellar tissue. In PFS, the anti-inflammatory actions of NALL can contribute to a reduction in neuroinflammation-induced neuronal damage. By decreasing the inflammatory response, NALL could alleviate secondary injury to cerebellar neurons, preserve synaptic function, and support the reparative processes necessary for functional recovery. Attenuation of neuroinflammation can also mitigate edema formation and stabilize the blood–brain barrier, further protecting neuronal environments. This could facilitate the reestablishment of cerebellar circuitry and enhance neuroplasticity, promoting improvements in the motor and speech functions affected by PFS. Therefore, the anti-inflammatory properties of NALL represent a potential therapeutic mechanism to address the neuroinflammatory aspects of the pathophysiology of PFS, which could improve the efficacy of rehabilitation strategies and improve patient outcomes.

Modulation of dopaminergic neurotransmission

Motor, cognitive, and speech impairments associated with PFS are primarily attributable to diminished cortical excitation following surgical disruption of the DTC pathway.^{(p3),(p25)} This pathway is instrumental in conveying excitatory cerebellar output to the cerebral cortex, thereby facilitating motor coordination, speech articulation, and higher-order cognitive processes. When surgical intervention in the posterior fossa compromises the integrity of the DTC pathway, the resultant cortical hypoactivity often manifests as ataxia, mutism, and emotional lability.^(p26) To mitigate these deficits, ADLL appears to enhance cortical excitation through the modulation of dopaminergic neurotransmission within the cortico–striato–thalamo-cortical loop, an alternative circuit heavily reliant on dopaminergic signaling to regulate motor and cognitive functions. Empirical evidence suggests that ADLL augments dopaminergic transmission by increasing DAT binding and enhancing dopaminergic activity in crucial nigrostriatal regions, notably the striatum and substantia nigra.^(p115) This effect in turn potentiates inhibitory output from the striatum to the SNpr and the internal segment of the globus pallidus (SNpr–GPi complex), thereby diminishing GABAergic suppression of thalamic projections. Such disinhibition leads to heightened thalamic input to the cortex,^(p136) potentially compensating for the reduced cerebellar excitation seen in PFS and consequently restoring motor coordination, cognitive functions, and speech production. Moreover, the dopaminergic modulation exerted by ADLL aligns with existing evidence supporting dopaminergic pharmacological interventions aimed at enhancing cortical excitability and alleviating PFS symptomatology.^{(p50),(p51),(p52)} Autoradiographic analyses further indicate that ADLL preferentially accumulates in regions responsible for motor control, such as the putamen, globus pallidus, and substantia nigra.^{(p115),(p117)} These regions constitute integral components of the basal ganglia, which interact closely with cerebellar outputs to regulate voluntary movement, motor learning, and coordination.^{(p137),(p138)} Within these areas, ADLL is posited to modulate neuronal excitability, synaptic transmission, and metabolic activity, thus supporting dopaminergic neuron function and fostering more efficient processing of motor

commands. Notably, recent [¹⁸F]FDG PET data from patients with cerebellar ataxia treated with ADLL have demonstrated increased metabolic activity in cortical sensorimotor and premotor areas, despite persistently reduced cerebellar metabolism.^(p77) These findings imply that ADLL might enhance motor function and facilitate functional recovery even in the context of sustained deficits in cerebellar output.

Implications for clinical application

Although preclinical and clinical studies indicate that ADLL and NALL might have therapeutic effects on the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying PFS, there is currently a paucity of direct studies that have specifically examined its effects in PFS. Therefore it is imperative that rigorous clinical trials be conducted to establish the therapeutic utility and safety profile of this agent in this specific context. The favorable safety record of ADLL and NALL in other neurological conditions supports their candidacy for clinical investigation in patients with PFS. Emerging evidence suggests that the pharmacological effects of ADLL are enantiomer-specific, with NALL demonstrating superior neurotherapeutic properties compared with NADL. Preclinical studies have indicated that NALL might be more effective than ADLL in improving neurological outcomes, possibly because of its augmented capacity to modulate metabolic pathways, reduce oxidative stress, and provide neuroprotective effects. In light of these insights, it seems reasonable to suggest that NALL might confer greater therapeutic benefits in PFS than ADLL. The enhanced pharmacological actions of NALL, particularly in the stabilization of neuronal membrane potential, metabolic support, antioxidative protection, and anti-inflammatory effects, position it as a potentially more effective agent to address the multifaceted pathophysiology of PFS. Therefore, it would seem beneficial for future clinical trials to consider evaluating NALL alongside ADLL, to elucidating their respective efficacies and safety profiles in the pediatric population predominantly affected by PFS. Careful pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies are essential to determine optimal dosing regimens that maximize therapeutic benefits while minimizing potential risks. Long-term follow-up studies are necessary to assess the sustainability of the therapeutic effects and monitor for delayed adverse outcomes.

Integration of NALL into the perioperative management of PFS can involve the administration of the compound not only postoperatively, but also preoperatively. This approach might enhance neural resilience to surgical stress. Administration of NALL prior to surgery has the potential to mitigate the deleterious effects of surgical trauma by stabilizing neuronal membranes, improving metabolic capacity, reducing oxidative stress, and attenuating neuroinflammation. This preoperative intervention can serve to prime the neural environment, thus reducing the extent of injury and promoting more favorable postoperative outcomes. Furthermore, an investigation of the potential for NALL to be used in conjunction with existing rehabilitation strategies, such as physical therapy, occupational therapy, and speech therapy, could provide valuable insights into comprehensive care approaches that address both neurological recovery and functional rehabilitation. An investigation into

whether NALL can enhance the efficacy of these interventions throughout the perioperative period might result in the development of optimized treatment protocols for patients at risk of developing PFS. Given the complexity and multifactorial nature of PFS, a multidisciplinary approach to clinical research is required. It will be essential to collaborate with neurosurgeons, neurologists, neuropharmacologists, pediatricians, and rehabilitation specialists to design and implement clinical studies that adequately assess the impact of NALL on functional recovery, neurodevelopmental outcomes, and overall quality of life in patients with PFS.

An important challenge in optimizing the therapeutic potential of NALL is to overcome the limitations imposed by saturable intestinal transport and extensive first-pass deacetylation, which can significantly reduce systemic exposure following oral administration. In this context, the parenteral formulation offers a promising alternative. Preclinical solubilization protocols have demonstrated that NALL can be safely formulated as a sterile isotonic solution by transient alkaline dissolution followed by adjustment of the pH to the physiological range, yielding concentrations suitable for intravenous administration.^(p105) This route not only ensures complete bioavailability and precise pharmacokinetic control, but also allows reliable systemic delivery during critical perioperative windows when enteral absorption might be compromised. As such, the development of a parenteral formulation of NALL could broaden its clinical applicability in acute neurological settings, including perioperative management of PFS, and warrants prioritization in future pharmacological and translational research.

As clinical applications of NALL are explored, it is important to consider not only the core features of PFS such as ataxia, mutism, and emotional lability, but also associated ocular-motor disturbances that might impact recovery and quality of life. Among these, central vestibular nystagmus has been observed in a subset of patients,^{(p139),(p140)} reflecting dysfunction in both cerebellar and supranuclear gaze-control pathways.^(p5) The therapeutic potential of NALL might therefore extend beyond the traditional clinical endpoints of motor and speech recovery. By restoring the physiological inhibitory output of floccular Purkinje cells, NALL could help normalize gaze-holding function compromised by cerebellar injury. Specifically, enhanced inhibition of vestibular nuclei, particularly the medial and superior vestibular nuclei in the brainstem, might recalibrate eye movement stability at the subcortical level. In addition to restoring cerebellar inhibition, NALL's ability to stabilize neuronal membrane potential could further contribute to the regulation of tonic output from these nuclei. Simultaneously, its modulatory effect on dopaminergic neurotransmission within cortico-striato-thalamo-cortical pathways might strengthen supranuclear control of eye movements, thus providing an effective bypass around damaged DTC circuits. This dual mechanism, combining brainstem level recalibration with cortical level suppression of abnormal ocular oscillations, is consistent with clinical observations of reduced central nystagmus velocity following treatment with ADLL/NALL in patients with central vestibular disorders.^{(p81),(p96),(p141)}

Ethical considerations are paramount, particularly when involving pediatric patients in clinical trials. Ensuring informed consent, minimizing patient risk, and adhering to stringent regulatory standards is critical. The stratification of patients based

on the severity of the symptoms of PFS, the timing of intervention, and individual variability in response to NALL might facilitate the generation of more precise data on efficacy, thus allowing the development of personalized treatment strategies.

The potential of NALL to address multiple aspects of the pathophysiology of PFS, potentially with greater efficacy than ADLL, makes it a compelling candidate for clinical application. Through careful and comprehensive clinical investigation, NALL could emerge as a valuable addition to the therapeutic arsenal for PFS, offering hope for improved neurological outcomes and quality of life for affected patients. Translating these preclinical findings into clinical practice could signify a significant advance in the management of this challenging and deteriorating syndrome, potentially setting new standards for therapeutic intervention in pediatric neurorehabilitation.

Concluding remarks

Treatment of PFS represents a significant clinical challenge because of its multifactorial pathophysiology and profound impact on motor, speech, and cognitive functions in pediatric patients following posterior fossa surgery. It is becoming increasingly evident that ADLL and its enantiomer NALL represent promising pharmacological candidates to address the neurophysiological disruptions underlying PFS. The reviewed evidence highlights the diverse therapeutic mechanisms of ADLL and NALL, including stabilization of neuronal membrane potentials, enhancement of energy metabolism, antioxidant effects, anti-inflammatory properties, and modulation of dopaminergic neurotransmission, all of which could mitigate the various impairments seen in PFS.

Despite encouraging preclinical data, translating these findings into clinical applications requires rigorous validation through well-designed clinical trials. Future studies should not only compare the efficacy and safety profiles of ADLL and NALL, but also explore their roles as perioperative interventions potentially providing neuroprotection and reducing the impact of surgical trauma. The integration of pharmacotherapy with multidisciplinary rehabilitation strategies is crucial to optimize functional recovery and improve the quality of life of children affected by PFS.

The potential superiority of NALL over ADLL in improving neurological outcomes through its enhanced neurotherapeutic properties positions it as a particularly compelling agent for future clinical research. Given the current gap in direct evidence for ADLL and NALL in PFS, a focused interdisciplinary approach involving neurosurgeons, neurologists, pharmacologists, and rehabilitation specialists is imperative to establish the roles of these agents in the comprehensive care of patients with PFS. Ultimately, the successful integration of NALL or ADLL into clinical practice could offer new hope for reducing the burden of PFS, improving neurological resilience, and enhancing recovery in this vulnerable population.

Author contributions

P. V. conceived the idea for the study and was the primary author of the manuscript. **J. H.** provided suggestions for improving the readability of the text and conducted continuous revi-

sions throughout the writing process. **M. G. L.** and **M. B.**, as both academic and clinical neurologists, assessed the clinical impact and reviewed the manuscript for accurate terminology.

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Declarations of interest

No interests are declared.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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